

Letter of Acceptance

Dear Theo Tsenis,

On behalf of the Review Committee for the Eighteenth International Conference on Climate Change: Impacts & Responses, 20-22 April 2026 at University of the Aegean, Rhodes, Greece, + Online this letter confirms your presentation proposal, Hybrid Ground–Aerial Forest Inventory Using Quadraped Lidar DBH Ground Truth for Allometric Calibration of Drone-Based Crown Measurements has been accepted. We believe that your presentation and participation in general discussions will make a significant contribution to the conference.

The annual conference is an integral component of the Climate Change: Impacts & Responses Research Network. Founded in 2009, the Climate Change: Impacts & Responses Research Network is brought together by a common concern for the science of, and social responses to, climate change.

You can find regularly updated information about the conference on our website: <https://on-climate.com/2026-conference> Should you require further information or have any questions, please visit: <https://cgscholar.com/events/>

We do hope you will be able to attend this important and timely event.

Regards,

Dr. Phillip Kalantzis Cope
Chief Social Scientist
Common Ground Research Networks